

A Facilitated Construction Robot Programming Approach using Building Information Modelling

Michael Terzer¹, Tobit Flatscher^{1,2}, Marco Magri¹, Simone Garbin¹, Julius Emig¹, and Andrea Giusti¹

Abstract—Classical robot-programming approaches often require the definition of rigid sequences of elementary motions and actions by expert robot programmers through coding. Such solutions are suitable for environments that are more structured and less dynamic with respect to construction ones. We propose a different approach with a novel software architecture that exploits Building Information Modelling (BIM) data for facilitating robot-programming and deployment in construction. It includes mission parametrization and customization tools that abstract elementary robot functionality in terms of behaviors, that can be easily understood, assembled, and adapted on-site by non-expert programmers. We verify the effectiveness of our proposed approach by considering the execution of a spray-painting use-case for interior walls and a usability study.

Index Terms—Construction robotics, robot programming, building information modelling, behavior trees

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics applications e.g., from manufacturing and logistics to construction [1], often require expert programmers for coding and deploying the available robotic systems with suitable motions. However, programmers with the required knowledge might be unavailable and classical coding of each task from elementary robot motions can be time consuming and rigid [2]. For these reasons, the need for tools that allow robot behaviors to be specified in an intuitive and flexible way, and that can be easily understood by domain experts and end-users alike, becomes prominent [3]. Contrary to structured manufacturing environments, construction sites are dynamic and unstructured with changing ambient conditions, requiring flexible solutions for the deployment of robotics in practice.

The digitalization of the building design process has been targeted widely with the introduction of Building Information Modelling (BIM) [4]. Most of the results involving BIM for construction robotics are limited to exploiting pure geometric information: In [5] the authors propose a bridge between the middleware Robot Operating System (ROS) and a BIM model, showing its application to on-site construction robotics with construction time-dependent building elements and dynamic obstacles. Similarly, the authors of [6] extend the conventional localization and mapping with reference points of an existing BIM model. In [7], automated task

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¹Fraunhofer Italia Research, Via Alessandro Volta 13a, 39100 Bolzano, Italy { michael.terzer, marco.magri, simone.garbin, julius.emig, andrea.giusti } @fraunhofer.it, ²Oxford Robotics Institute, University of Oxford, 23 Banbury Road, tobit@robots.ox.ac.uk

Fig. 1. The autonomous mobile robot BALTO employed in the use-case of spray painting interior walls, showing the execution of a parametrized mission (A). The mission can be parametrized by a non-expert user by specifying a spraying area through a user interface (B) as detailed in Section II-E.

planning of a wall painting task in simulation by using the construction schedule contained in a BIM file was investigated. On the other hand only few publications exploit the semantic information contained in BIM models. During the COVID-19 pandemic, a ROS-BIM interface [5] has been extended to use the BIM model for both navigation and extraction of poses and types of objects to be autonomously disinfected by BALTO robots [8]. The authors of [9], provide a mobile robot with semantic information extracted from a BIM model for a navigation use-case.

The above-mentioned efforts on providing semantic information of the environment from BIM to the robot can reduce the deployment time of robotic systems. On the other hand, the composition and customization of the robots behaviors remain largely dependent on expert coding competencies and can thus complicate and slow down the deployment of construction robots.

We present a novel facilitated-programming architecture for construction robots that includes: i) a user-interface for mission parametrization based on BIM-data, ii) a hierarchical and graphical abstraction of robotic skills, iii) robot mission modelling and execution based on behavior trees.

With respect to other existing behavior-based programming architectures such as [10] and [11], we introduce novel components with ROSBIM and a skill library that supports parametrizations from BIM data

Fig. 2. Component diagram of our proposed architecture: The generic primitive skills can be assembled to realize generic composite skills and tasks before they are parametrized (with parameters from a BIM model) for a specific mission.

along with a dedicated mission generator component. An additional advancement with respect to other existing solutions limited to robotic navigation such as [9], is that our proposed architecture focuses on the programming and deployment process of mobile robot manipulators in construction in a comprehensive manner: considering mission-tasks definition by users, arm-motion planning, autonomous navigation, calibration and perception skills.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II details the design of our software architecture. Section III presents a case study with a mobile robot manipulator that verifies the applicability of our approach in simulation, an experiment and a usability study. In particular, we consider a spray painting task of interior walls (as shown in Fig. 1). Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section IV, with a discussion on known limitations and envisioned extensions.

II. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

Our proposed architecture is illustrated at a glance in the diagram of Fig. 2, which indicates its main components with a reference to the subsections of their description.

A. Execution model

Robotic software is commonly structured in hierarchical software layers. Architectures based on task abstraction are often separated in three distinct software layers [12]:

- on the top layer, the reasoning level, long-term solutions to complex high-level problems are developed either by manual design, planning methods or learning-based approaches;
- the middle layer, the executive level, takes the directives of the top layer and translates them for the bottom layer into low-level behavior at the appropriate time, monitors the execution and handles exceptions;
- the bottom layer, also denoted as the behavior or reactive level, handles the low-level control of the robotic hardware.

In the middle layer, hierarchical finite state machines (HFSM) are often used [12], [13]. However in recent years, behavior trees (BT) have proven to be more flexible [14], [15], therefore we base our execution model on BT.

BT are directed acyclic graphs consisting of nodes and edges connecting them. Child-less nodes are referred to as leaves while the parent-less base node is the root node. The non-leaf nodes (control-flow nodes) are responsible for the task-switching-logic between the execution nodes, which might either be condition nodes (that examine the system state), action nodes (that alter the system state) or entire behavior trees (subtrees). The nodes may have input and output arguments which are shared through a global (and potentially scoped) key-value storage (blackboard). For further detail we redirect the reader to [16] and [17].

B. User and skill hierarchy

Similarly to [11] and [18], we refer to a primitive skill as an elementary functionality directly related to the underlying robot hardware. Primitive skills can be combined hierarchically to more complex composite skills which can be either generic, an abstract parametrized behavior, or specific, with parameters for a particular situation.

With reference to Fig. 3, we introduce the composite skills (C-skills) and primitive skills (P-skills), where C-skills are formed by multiple P-skills. For example, action and leaf nodes, which are implemented as behavior trees, are C-skills. Fig. 4 shows a set of P-skills that could be arranged in a subtree to form a C-skill.

A mission, is defined by the sequence of tasks and composite skills to be performed, as well as their corresponding parameters. Once defined, a mission can then be sent to a behavior tree executor that executes it and additionally exposes the possibility to pause, stop or restart running tasks as well as load different skill libraries.

We define the robotic skill levels by targeting specific classes of users:

- an expert robot-programmer implements P-skills on code-level and provides the necessary interfaces from low-level software components to the behavior tree libraries;
- a mid-level user constructs custom parametrized primitive skills in the form of generic parametrizable subtrees using a graphic user interface. Even with a limited knowledge of robotics but an understanding of

Fig. 3. Illustration of our proposed mission, task and skill hierarchy. C-skill stands for composite skill, P-skill stands for primitive skill. A mission can include up to n tasks, up to m C-skills and up to k P-skills, whereas a task can include up to j C-skills and up to i P-skills.

the final application, mid-level users are expected to define C-skills or tasks for the end-user;

- an end-user regulates and dispatches the provided missions based on BIM data at the time of deployment.

C. Architecture implementation

Our software architecture uses the Robot Operating System (ROS¹) (ROS Noetic on Linux Ubuntu 22.04). As a basis for the execution layer and according to the comparison of BT libraries in [19], we choose the popular *BehaviorTree.CPP 4.X* library². We implement behavior tree leaves as P-skills for popular ROS toolchains as illustrated in Fig. 4 (e.g. services and action nodes for motion planning and navigation as well as for managing ROS-controllers). The functionalities of the behavior tree nodes are implemented by customly developed skill libraries. Any P-skill is specified as a combination of a C++ library and an XML file describing its interface, on the other hand any C-skill takes the form of an XML subtree. In addition to the predefined skills one might specify and load custom P-skills.

D. BIM integration

The architecture we propose, includes a layer that enriches the world model with semantic information (e.g., relation of objects to each other, bounding boxes, object-types) by exploiting the Industry Foundation Class (IFC)³. For this, a new plug-in-based interface for ROS to BIM, called ROSBIM, is developed by building upon our previous results in [8]. The core is the ROSBIM manager, which loads a BIM model and controls the state-machine of the individual plug-ins whose states can be: loaded, running, and stopped. Each plug-in offers services and information to the user via ROS services and topics, providing for example a map for navigation as well as a 3D model for visualization.

Fig. 4. UML package diagram of the implemented primitive skills for motion planning, navigation, control and standard communication.

For providing a map, the occupancy grid map of a selected building floor is extracted with the ROSBIM *CreateMap* plug-in. The building is sliced and each object is projected onto a horizontal plane in order to obtain a two-dimensional map of a building or construction site in the area of interest. For providing a 3D model of the building, the BIM model is split up into walls, doors, windows and furnitures, and finally, it is exported with the ROSBIM *ExportGeometry* plug-in. The service to export IFC objects filters for elements of interests e.g., *IfcDoor*, *IfcWall*, *IfcFurniture* and *IfcWindow* elements. Then, the geometry is exported through a mesh file (COLLADA file-format) accompanied by an IFC-file, either as an entire model or as separate ones for each element. Finally, it is possible to load the elements as custom markers into the 3D visualization of the graphic user interface.

The ROSBIM architecture allows one to abstract the BIM interface as a backend. The current implementation uses the *IfcOpenShell*⁴ library. Alternatives like *BIM-server*⁵ could also be integrated.

E. User interface

We allow a lay user to define and deploy a robotic mission on-site through a user interface which embeds a custom RViz⁶ visualization of the shared environment including the robot, as well as a 3D model of the building from BIM. We allow the user to interact with geometric markers and select the elements of the building for which a certain task should be performed on. The plug-in for the painting mission (as shown in Fig. 5) queries ROSBIM for the semantic information of task relevant objects (e.g. bounding-box, location or object-type), allows to parametrize the task and to dispatch the mission. Furthermore, the visualization is augmented with the sensor data of the robot so that the user is made aware of how the robot perceives its surroundings. The user interface runs on a pilot computer which is connected over wireless network with the robot.

¹<https://www.ros.org> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

²<https://github.com/BehaviorTree/BehaviorTree.CPP> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

³<https://www.iso.org/standard/70303.html> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

⁴<https://ifcopenshell.org/> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

⁵<https://bimserver.org/> last accessed on 13/05/2024.

⁶<http://wiki.ros.org/rviz> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

Fig. 5. Extract from the user interface for illustration. The robot setup is shown in the visualization pane including the costmap on the floor showing the occupancy grid map exported with the ROSBIM `ExportMap` plugin. The cyan highlighted bounding box represents the selected wall element exported through the ROSBIM `ExportGeometry` plugin and visualized as a custom marker. The blue and red arrows can be dragged to position and scale the spraying area. Clicking on the marker allows the user to dispatch the mission on the selected wall based on the configured area.

III. DEMONSTRATION WITH A USE CASE

To verify the applicability of our proposed architecture, we implement in simulation as well as in real-world demonstrations a construction relevant use-case. The following subsections detail the use-case, the test environment, the robot setup, and the experimental results.

A. Use-case Description

The application we consider is inspired from the use-cases of the EU Horizon 2020 project *CONConfigurable Collaborative Robot Technologies*, *CONCERT*⁷ for short. The project focuses on the development and application of modular reconfigurable robots for construction sites to assist the human workers for repetitive and dangerous tasks.

We consider a construction relevant use-case for spray-painting of interior walls. The test environment we consider is the crane hall (see Fig. 5) of the NOI Techpark, Bolzano (Italy), or its virtual counterpart in simulation, based on the Gazebo simulator⁸.

For the real use-case, we use a lightweight movable partitioning wall (see Fig. 6) and applied carton as a protection layer. For geo-referencing the BIM model, the door area of the crane hall is replaced by an IFC wall and substituted in reality with the partitioning wall. We use a green water-based acrylic paint color, to get a similar consistency to conventional wall paint, we liquify the acrylic color with water. For every experiment we attached layers of paper strip with white tape to the wall.

B. Robot setup

The mobile robot manipulator BALTO, developed in [8], is used for the execution of the use-case. BALTO is composed

of an omnidirectional mobile base (Neobotix MPO-700) combined with a seven degrees-of-freedom robotic arm (Franka Emika Panda arm). The perception system for navigation includes two lidar scanners (SICK S300 Expert), mounted to two opposite corners of the mobile platform. The perception-capabilities of the robot are further enhanced by a color and depth camera (Intel Realsense D435), which is mounted through a custom-made 3D printed support. We mount a paint spray gun (Einhell TC-SY 18/60 Li-Solo) through a custom designed end-effector. To be able to grasp tools with a robotic gripper, the holding support and activation of the spray paint gun is composed of a two finger gripper (Robotiq 2F-85) with custom 3D printed fingers. The paint spray gun can be activated through a trigger. By pressing the trigger lightly, the robot activates the air-fan; by pressing the trigger further, the robot regulates the amount of color applied to the air-stream.

C. Use-case demonstrations and experiments

Considering the wall painting use-case, the parametrization of the painting mission is performed through an interactive process. The user selects wall objects as targets for the mission using the corresponding plugin. As soon as a marker of a wall is selected with the `SelectMarker` tool, a rectangular spraying area and interactive arrows appear on the selected element (see Fig. 5). The arrows can be dragged to position and scale the area. A button dialog implemented through the interactive-marker-control menu is used to dispatch the mission. A dedicated spraying mission generator automatically generates the waypoints for the mobile base and for the robotic arm end-effector. All waypoints are specified with reference to the task frame which is shown in Fig. 5.

The execution of the mission is sent through a ROS-service call to the underlying behavior tree executor. The parameters

⁷<https://concertproject.eu/> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

⁸<https://gazebosim.org/home> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

Fig. 6. The BALTO robot performing the painting use case on a carton covered partitioning wall. The grey shaded region, representing the wall element of the building model, is replicated in real-world by a carton covered partitioning wall. The robot motions are divided into three sections along the spraying area. The first section's spraying trajectory is highlighted in green.

are the reference coordinates for the painting motions and the generated waypoints. The complexity of the task is hidden behind a specific `WallPainting` composite skill which is composed of primitive arm-motion, navigation-, calibration- and robot specific spray-painting-skills. Since the global pose of the robot is affected by errors coming from the navigation, localization and perception system, a precise pose of the robot with respect to the wall element is obtained using a calibration-skill based on ArUco-code detection and the camera mounted on the end-effector when required.

The underlying BT can be changed through a graphical behavior tree tool (Groot⁹) without the intervention of an expert robot-programmer. In particular, the editor allows one to add or remove nodes and to arrange the tree structure by drag and drop. Furthermore, through the same tool, the discrete execution of the behavior tree nodes can be monitored, logged as well as replayed at a later time providing thus the possibility to debug the execution of the behavior tree.

D. Usability-study with wall painting use-case

We assess the effectiveness of our proposed approach by means of a usability-study with 5 lay users for the above-mentioned wall-painting use case. For each lay user we performed two tests. We allow the user to deploy a robot mission with standard tools in the first test. In the second test we allow the user to adopt our facilitated programming approach.

In the first test we measure the time that a lay user needs to manually teach the robot poses. The registration of the poses has been implemented by a Python script. The registered

waypoints for the mobile base and robotic arm, are saved in the same format that the spraying mission generator would generate. At the end of the test the mission and its behavior tree can be executed: the robotic arm moves to the transport pose, then the mobile base moves to the mobile-base-waypoint, then the robotic arm moves through the created S-like trajectory and its arm-waypoints.

In the the second test, a lay user defines the robot mission from our user-interface with the BIM-based mission parametrization capabilities. We measure the time a user needs to select a wall, regulate the painting area with the help of the interactive markers and dispatch the mission. In this case, the mobile robot pose and the arm-waypoints can be generated by the spraying mission generator.

The results show that the average time for execution of the first test is 3.01 minutes while for the second test the average is 18 seconds. This corresponds to a faster mission parametrization using our tools of approximately 10 times. Please note that the tests did not include a geometrical fine-tuning of the poses. Comparing the effort needed to precisely align multiple robot poses in the first test and to align the painting area to the environment one time in the second test, it becomes evident that significantly more effort would be needed for manual teach-in without our approach.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper a novel way to facilitate construction-robot programming is presented, that leverages on the tight integration of a BIM model as a geometric and semantic environment model into a mission and task parametrization architecture based on behavior trees. In the proposed solution primitive skills can be composed hierarchically to more complex parametrizable behaviors: composite skills, tasks,

⁹<https://www.behaviortree.dev/groot/> last accessed on 12/04/2024.

and ultimately, a mission. When parametrizing the composite skills for a specific task, the user might refer to semantic information stored inside a BIM model via the integration of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) format through ROSBIM. We provide a user with the possibility to compose and modify existing tasks without the need for text-based syntax wherefore programming is evidently facilitated for non-expert users. Additionally the ability to refer to semantic objects information rather than three-dimensional poses data only, increases flexibility and reduces complexity. These advantages were verified with the execution of a construction relevant use-case for autonomous painting of interior walls and a usability study.

Future work will be devoted to extend the usability study to include more users. Additionally, we plan to test the proposed approach on further use-cases for collaborative transportation of construction material and drilling into walls. We plan to conduct these experiments with a different robotic platform, in order to show the simple transferability and hardware independency of our approach.

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